

ATLAS OF VARIANT EFFECTS ALLIANCE

2023 ANNUAL REPORT

Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance

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THANK YOU

A message from the co-chairs of the AVE executive committee

It is customary at the end of the year to reflect on an organization's accomplishments. Those of us who are privileged to serve on the Executive Committee of the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance are especially proud of 2023. As we all recognize, it was:

- A year of significant growth in numbers and diversity of the Alliance's membership;
- A year of unprecedented progress toward our goal of a comprehensive atlas of variant effect maps of all segments of DNA that are of biomedical relevance to assist in the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of disease; and
- A year highlighted by our 6th annual Mutational Scanning Symposium, held at the Wellcome Genome Campus in the UK (first time outside of North America), in which more than 400 scientists, clinicians, and industry leaders (in-person and online) collaboratively shared insights and observations. Of particular note was the satellite workshop on the 'Clinical Applications of MAVE data' that was co-organised with the 'Curating the Clinical Genome' team where we made real progress on ensuring that the efforts of Alliance members can be rapidly and robustly translated into faster, better diagnoses for patients.

These and other activities covered in this annual report underscore the uncompromising commitment of the Alliance's 500-plus members to sharing their work openly toward a greater public good.

We want to thank all those who contributed time, talent, and treasure in 2023 to making our Alliance a productive and respected scientific collaborative endeavour, including, but by no means limited to, the Executive Committee and Workstream members as well as

Symposium speakers, sponsors and attendees. We all have much to look forward to in 2024 and beyond, as we seek to realise the potential of genomics to transform the lives and livelihoods of those affected by disease.

Matt Hurles and Doug Fowler

Professor Matthew Hurles [he, him]
Director, Wellcome Sanger Institute

Douglas M. Fowler, Ph. D. [he, him]
Professor, Department of Genome Sciences
University of Washington School of Medicine

Cover image description: People moving amongst and inspecting larger than life Variant Effect Maps of clinically important genes (BRCA1, HMBS, MTHFR and TDP-43). Background is a world map with a chromosome ideogram overlay. Art by Uta Mackensen (CC BY-ND).

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TOWARDS AN ATLAS OF VARIANT EFFECTS

The Atlas of Variant Effects (AVE) Alliance is an international collaborative founded in 2020 whose efforts are focused on developing, disseminating and democratizing the foundational experimental and analytical technologies for mapping variant effects. Our collective vision is to create a comprehensive atlas (collection of variant effect maps) for important regions of human and human pathogen genomes that could ultimately assist in the diagnosis, prognosis and treatment of disease

OBJECTIVES OF THE ALLIANCE

1. Bring together data generators, curators and consumers, along with funders and other stakeholders from across the globe to set standards, share tools and develop strategy.
2. Facilitate production of a collection of comprehensive variant effect maps (a nucleotide-resolution atlas) that could ultimately assist in the diagnosis, prognosis, and treatment of disease.
3. Create community-driven, democratic resources for sharing, discovering and analyzing large-scale variant effect data.

OUR VALUES AND PRINCIPLES

- Inclusivity
- Open Access Science
- Research Excellence and Integrity
- Respect, Relevance, Reciprocity, Responsibility, Relationships

LEADERSHIP

Executive Committee: David Adams, Doug Fowler (co-chair), Anna Gloyn, Irene Gallego Romero, Matthew Hurles (co-chair), Debora Marks, J.T. Neal, Frederick 'Fritz' Roth, Alan Rubin, Lea Starita

David Adams

Doug Fowler

Anna Gloyn

Irene Gallego Romero

Matthew Hurles

Debora Marks

JT Neal

Frederick (Fritz) Roth

Alan Rubin

Lea Starita

Program Management and Administrative Support: Lara Muffley and Alex Hopkins

Communications Working Group: Lara Muffley, Dean Owen, Rachael Smith, Alexandra Canet

Workstream and Committee co-chairs:

- Clinical Variant Interpretation (CVI) Lea Starita and Clare Turnbull
- Data Coordination and Dissemination (DCD) Alan Rubin
- Experimental Technology and Standards (ETS) Benedetta Bolognesi and Andrew Glazer
- Analysis, Modelling and Prediction (AMP) Joseph Marsh
- Outreach Diversity and Inclusion Committee (ODIC) Willow Coyote-Maestas and Irene Gallego Romero

Variant Effect Seminar Series (VESS) Planning Committee: Ohanna Bezerra, Diego Calderon, Yann Ilboudo, Mariano Martín and Adrine de Souza.

INSTITUTIONAL AFFILIATIONS

The Brotman Baty Institute and the Department of Genome Sciences at the University of Washington, Seattle, USA, provide administrative support on behalf of AVE. The Executive Committee's institutional affiliations are also depicted below.

OUR MEMBERS

Alliance Members : We currently have over 500 members from the following 39 countries: Australia, Austria, Belgium, Canada, China, Denmark, Ecuador, Estonia, France, Germany, India, Iran, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Korea, Latvia, Luxembourg, Mexico, the Netherlands, Nepal, New Zealand, Norway, the Philippines, Poland, Russia, Saudi Arabia, Singapore, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, Ukraine, the United Kingdom, and the United States.

Global representation of Alliance members

HIGHLIGHTS FROM 2023

Membership Growth

- The Alliance exceeded 500 members from nearly 40 nations in 2023. These individuals include early and mid-career scientists, along with senior-level individuals in industry, government, and academia, as well as patient advocacy groups and foundations - a total of more than 250 institutions. The overwhelming majority (80 percent) serve in the academic sector.
- Membership is geographically diverse. More than 50 percent are in the United States, with 15 percent in the UK, 7 percent in Canada, and 3 percent in Australia.

New Resources

- MAVE Data Analysis Tools <https://www.varianteffect.org/analysis-tools>
- Variant Effect Predictors <https://www.varianteffect.org/veps>
- Protocol Repository [AVE protocols.io workspace](https://www.varianteffect.org/ave-protocols)

Leadership

- Irene Gallego Romero [joined the AVE Executive Committee](#) (May 2023)
- Victoria Nicole Parikh and Melina Claussnitzer, previous co-chairs for ETS workstream, handed over the baton to Benedetta Bolognesi and Andrew Glazer (Feb 2023)
- Debbie Marks and Ben Lehner, previous co-chairs for AMP workstream, handed over the baton to Joseph Marsh (Feb 2023)

Variant Effects Seminar Series (VESS)

- [42 speakers](#) from 2020-2023
- New members of the [organizing committee](#) (Ohanna Bezerra, Mariano Martín)
- Organizing committee member departures (Steven Erwood, Mireia Seuma)

Mutational Scanning Symposium and Workshop

- [6th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#) 407 attendees from 50 countries, Hinxton, UK and online (Jul 2023)
- Clinical Application of MAVE Data [workshop](#) 44 participants, Hinxton, UK (Jul 2023)

Miscellaneous

- [Youtube channel](#) (over 500 subscribers and over 32K views as of Dec 2023)
- The AVE Alliance became an [organizational member](#) of the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) (Feb 2023)
- Formation of a Mave Rare Disease Podcast Exploratory Committee - led by ETS workstream member Alex Nguyen Ba (Aug 2023)
- [Collection of articles](#) focused on multiplex assays of variant effect published in Genome Biology (Jul 2023)
- [“An Atlas of Variant Effects to understand the genome at nucleotide resolution”](#) Alliance led correspondence piece published in Genome Biology as part of the collection mentioned above which outlines the vision for creating a comprehensive Atlas (Jul 2023)

WORKSTREAM PROGRESS

All workstreams and committees have been meeting by zoom regularly and working asynchronously throughout the year. Each group presented a short progress summary at the 2023 Mutational Scanning Symposium. Below is a summary of what was presented along with key updates.

The **Experimental Technology and Standards (ETS) workstream** led by Benedetta Bolognesi (IBEC, Barcelona, ESP) and Andrew Glazer (Vanderbilt U, Nashville TN, USA) facilitates the development, scaling, evaluation, comparison and dissemination of new MAVE methods.

This year, in close collaboration with the DCD workstream, ETS developed and implemented a validatable, computable list of [controlled vocabulary](#) terms for describing MAVE experiments that will enable users to find relevant experimental results in MaveDB and elsewhere.

ETS is also developing an [AVE protocols.io workspace](#) which will contain a MAVE protocols collection. ETS has [developed a guide](#) for how to create and publish a protocol in that space.

The structured or controlled vocabulary and standard is intended to give structure to minimum required information for data and meta-data sharing for scientists using variant effect mapping technology.

The **Analysis, Modelling and Prediction (AMP) workstream** led by Joseph Marsh (The University of Edinburgh, UK) promotes the development of computational tools and standards.

In 2023, this workstream with assistance from contributors Hasan Çubuk and Benjamin J. Livesey, developed two informational resources which are freely available on our website:

- Variant Effect Predictors <https://www.varianteffect.org/veps>
- MAVE Data Analysis Tools <https://www.varianteffect.org/analysis-tools>

The image displays two screenshots of the Atlas of Variant Effects website. The left screenshot shows the 'Variant Effect Predictors' page, which includes a navigation menu, a sub-header, a paragraph about computational approaches, a call-to-action link, and sections for 'Variant Effect Predictors' and 'Using VEPs'. The right screenshot shows the 'MAVE (Multiplexed Assays of Variant Effect) Data Analysis Tools' page, which includes a navigation menu, a sub-header, a paragraph about MAVE experiments, a list of three primary steps (Library generation, Variant selection, Variant scoring), and sections for 'Computational tools for scoring' and 'Variant scoring or analysis'.

Informational resources provided by the AMP workstream

The **Clinical Variant Interpretation (CVI) workstream** led by Clare Turnbull (ICR, London, UK) and Lea Starita (Brotman Baty Institute and Department of Genome Sciences, University of Washington, USA) develops recommendations for combining multiple datasets and orthogonal modalities for MAVE data validation. This year, CVI co-organized a 'Clinical Application of MAVE Data' Workshop to discuss the potential use of mutational scanning data in variant classification in clinical practice.

The CVI **Combining MAVE data sub-committee** (George Burghel, Jeff Calhoun, Daniel Jaraillo-Calle, Moez Dawood, Shawn Fayer, Sujatha Jagannathan, Elizabeth Radford, and Charlie Rowlands) is currently working on a commentary outlining the use case for combining multiple MAVE datasets as well as best practices to achieve outcomes such as improved pathogenicity classification.

Clare Turnbull and Shawn Fayer at the 'Clinical Application of MAVE Data' Workshop (Jul 2023)

The **Data Coordination and Dissemination (DCD)** workstream led by Alan Rubin (WEHI, Melbourne, AU) promotes the growth of the MAVE field by enabling sharing and management of MAVE data. In 2023, this workstream:

- Developed minimum information standards and a controlled vocabulary for MAVES in collaboration with the ETS workstream <https://arxiv.org/abs/2306.15113>

- Described a protocol for mapping MAVE variants to the human genome and applied it to MaveDB <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2023.06.20.545702v1>

Other accomplishments included applying the Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) VRS data standard for describing genomic variants to data in MaveDB. This, in turn, has and will continue to enable broad collaboration and data exchange among MaveDB, ClinGen Linked Data Hub, Ensembl, Shariant, DECIPHER, the Broad Institute Genomics 2 Proteins portal, and the UCSC Genome Browser.

An overview of the MAVE variant mapping method.

The **Outreach Diversity and Inclusion Committee (ODIC)** led by Willow Coyote-Maestas (UCSF, USA) and Irene Gallego Romero (St. Vincent's Institute of Medical Research, Melbourne, AU), has parallel inward and outward facing missions to 1) increase the diversity and inclusion within AVE 2) facilitate partnerships among the Alliance and

stakeholder communities; and 3) explore ethical and equitable MAVE design, execution and dissemination. This committee is actively working on a manuscript focused on how MAVEs can advance equity in genomic medicine.

MUTATIONAL SCANNING SYMPOSIUM

Each year, the Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance hosts the Mutational Scanning Symposium where experts in the fields of functional genomics, protein science, precision medicine, variant interpretation, and computational genetics come from around the world to connect, present their work, discuss new methods and provide insights into the future of this science.

Dave Adams and Matt Hurles co-hosts of the 6th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium

The [6th annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#) was held at the Wellcome Genome Campus in the UK (and online) July 13-14th, 2023. This year, the two-day program included a keynote lecture by Frederick 'Fritz' Roth, as well as 28 invited talks. There were a total of 407 attendees (217 in-person attendees plus another 190 participating virtually in real time) from 50 countries. Many speakers agreed to help create a community resource by making their talks permanently available on our affiliate [YouTube](#) channel.

The 2023 symposium was sponsored by the [Chan Zuckerberg Initiative](#), [Illumina](#), [Abcam](#), [Ambry Genetics](#), [AstraZeneca](#), [Congenica](#) and the [Brotman Baty Institute for Precision Medicine](#).

Mutational Scanning Symposium bursary recipients

You can also read more details about the symposium in the articles below:

- [Building an atlas of gene variants to understand health and disease - Wellcome Sanger Institute Blog](#) - Summary from the 6th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium
- [Following Up on MSS 2023: Perspectives from Two Participants](#) - Q&A with Raghavan Varadarajan and Yann Ilboudo
- [Exploring variant effects to advance precision medicine](#) - Post workshop and symposium synopsis by Sounak Sahu
- [MSS 2023 Planners Explore Expected Symposium Highlights and Opportunities](#) with Clare Turnbull and David Adams
- [What to Expect at the MSS 2023](#) - Q&A with Keynote Frederick (Fritz) Roth
- [Q&A with Xiaoyan "Isaac" Jia](#) - China-Based Scientist to Present at Upcoming Mutational Scanning Symposium
- [Collection of Alex Cagan Illustrations from the symposium](#)

Save the dates!

7th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium

May 22-24th, 2024

Broad Institute, Massachusetts, USA

8th Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium

May 21-23rd, 2025

Institute for Bioengineering of Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain

CLINICAL APPLICATION OF MAVE DATA WORKSHOP

On July 12th, 2023 a Clinical Application of MAVE Data workshop was held at the Wellcome Connecting Science Conference Centre in the UK. This meeting was jointly hosted by the scientific planning committees of 'Curating the Clinical Genome' and the 'Mutational Scanning Symposium'. 44 participants gathered in person to discuss the use of mutational scanning data in variant classification in clinical practice. A summary report manuscript has been submitted to the European Journal of Human Genetics (EJHG).

VARIANT EFFECTS SEMINAR SERIES (VESS)

This seminar series is a platform for early career scientists to share their research related to interpreting human genetic variation. In September of 2023, VESS celebrated its two-year anniversary!

Examples of Variant Effects Seminar Series flyers from 2023

VESS is spearheaded by Diego Calderon (Postdoctoral researcher at the University of Washington, USA), Yann Ilboudo (Research associate at McGill University, Canada) and Adrine de Souza (PhD student in the Department of Molecular Genetics at the University of Toronto, Canada).

In late 2023, the organizing committee welcomed two new members: Ohanna Bezerra (Postdoctoral Researcher in (Epi)Genomics, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, University of Toronto, Canada) and Mariano Martín (Postdoctoral Researcher with Benedetta Bolognesi's group at Institute for Bioengineering of Catalunya, Barcelona, Spain).

VESS organizing committee members: Diego Calderon, Yann Ilboudo, Adrine de Souza, Ohanna Bezerra and Mariano Martín.

The Alliance also sends thanks to our outgoing VESS organizing committee members Steven Erwood and Mireia Seuma who have helped make our series so successful.

The top five most viewed VESS videos in 2023 were:

- "[Disease variant prediction with deep generative models of evolutionary data](#)" Jonathan Frazer and Mafalda Dias (over 1.1K views)
- "[Phenotyping coding variants in cancer using Perturb-seq](#)" Oana Ursu (over 900 views)
- "[Saturation variant interpretation using prime editing](#)" Steven Erwood (over 700 views)
- "[Mapping the energetic and allosteric landscapes of protein binding domains](#)" André Faure (over 600 views)
- "[Genetic dissection of enhancer function](#)" Marty Yang (over 400 views)

NEWSWORTHY_MENTIONS

The Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance was mentioned in the news in 2023.

- [Map of disease-causing mutations in neurodevelopmental disorders and cancer revealed](#)
- [refget v2.0 links the hidden dictionaries of DNA](#)
- [The Sherlock Holmes moment](#)
- [Accidental Entrepreneur \(Interview with Matthew Hurles\)](#)
- [The diagnostic odyssey: A journey into genetic testing for rare diseases](#)
- [Understanding the role of Variants of Unknown Significance in rare disease](#)

Read them all here: <https://www.varianteffect.org/news>

PUBLICATIONS

The Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance was cited or mentioned in the following Scientific Publications in 2023.

- [Unified views on variant impact across many diseases](#) Kumar and Gerstein, Opinion piece, Trends in Genomics (Feb 2023)
- [Minimum information and guidelines for reporting a Multiplexed Assay of Variant Effect](#) Clausnitzer et al. arXiv Preprint (Jun 2023)
- [Mapping MAVE data for use in human genomics applications](#) Arbesfeld et al. BioRxiv Preprint (Jun 2023)
- [Article collection in Genome Biology: Towards an atlas of variant effects](#) Genome Biology (Jul 2023)
- [An Atlas of Variant Effects to understand the genome at nucleotide resolution](#) Fowler et al. Genome Biology (Jul 2023)
- [SUNi mutagenesis: Scalable and uniform nicking for efficient generation of variant libraries](#) Mighell et al. PlosOne (Jul 2023)
- [Predicting pathogenic protein variants](#) Marsh and Teichmann Science (Sept 2023)
- [Ensembl 2024](#) Harrison, et al. (Nov 2023)
- [Will variants of uncertain significance still exist in 2030?](#) Fowler and Rehm AJHG (Dec 2023)

CROSS CONSORTIA COLLABORATIONS

A National Human Genome Research Institute (NHGRI) led **Trans-variant Working Group** was established in 2023. This group includes representatives from various initiatives such as [ClinGen](#), [GREGoR](#), [HPRC](#), [IGVF](#) and the AVE Alliance to harmonize the gathering, analysis and clinical use of variant functional data. This collective discusses issues asynchronously on a dedicated slack channel and meets on a regular basis by zoom.

In late January 2023, a **Cross Consortium Communications Collective** was assembled in order to foster communication between groups with the goal of learning from each others' approaches and identifying synergistic outreach opportunities. This collective discusses issues asynchronously on a dedicated [GA4GH](#) slack channel.

On September 13th 2023, Alliance representatives Lea Starita, Doug Fowler, Alan Rubin, Melissa Cline and Lara Muffley participated in a **Cross-Consortium Meeting** hosted by NHGRI at Washington University, St. Louis to discuss how to build on existing collaborations between AVE, the Clinical Genome (ClinGen) Resource, the Genomics Research to Elucidate the Genetics of Rare Diseases (GREGoR), the Human Pangenome Reference Consortium (HPRC) and the Impact of Genomic Variation on Function (IGVF).

The objectives of the cross-consortium meeting were to:

- To Identify projects that will facilitate the goals or leverage the resources of one or more of the consortia.
- Identify areas of high interest requiring further consideration to determine barriers and possible solutions to help each other.

The NHGRI meeting report summary can be found here: <https://www.genome.gov/sites/default/files/media/files/2023-12/NHGRI-cross-consortia-day-2023-meeting-report.pdf>

MAVE RESOURCES AND TOOLS

Multiplexed assays of variant effects (MAVEs) allows the assessment (in a single experiment) of thousands of variants simultaneously. This technique, which harnesses the power of next-gen sequencing, yields large-scale data sets that can shed light on the functional consequences of protein variants and ultimately on the landscape of human genetic variation. The Alliance provides (and continually updates) a suite of resources and tools for variant effect mapping which include:

MAVEDB

MaveDB is the open source platform and database of record for variant effect mapping and the deposition of MAVE datasets. Currently there are over 300 MAVE Datasets deposited encompassing over three million variant effects.

This year, **downstream integrations of MaveDB data** included:

- UCSC Genome Browser Track (MAVE data added as a track hub)
- Genomics 2 Protein Portal (scores visible as heatmaps for available genes)
- [Ensembl](#) Variant Effect Predictor (MaveDB integration) ([MaveDB plugin](#))

Alan Rubin (chair of the DCD workstream) along with others in the Alliance are also currently 1) re-engineering [MaveDB](#) to enable federation with [ClinVar](#), [UniProt](#), [ClinGen](#), [Ensembl](#), [Shariant](#) and other entities and 2) developing a bidirectional interface from MaveDB to the ClinGen Linked Data Hub, which aggregates and delivers structured information about variant effects from literature curation and other resources.

Current datasets in MaveDB as of December 2023

MAVEREGISTRY

[MaveRegistry](#) is a platform to catalyze collaboration, reduce redundant efforts, allow stakeholders to nominate targets and enable tracking and sharing of progress on ongoing MAVE projects and stats. Over 200 MAVE projects from approximately 60 groups around the world have been publicly registered, and in 2023, 40 additional genes were nominated by users as being worthy of a MAVE project.

Amazing MAVE projects

TRACKED HERE

MaveRegistry is a collaborative resource for sharing progress on Multiplexed Assays of Variant Effect (MAVE).

Please cite: [Kuang et al. 2021](#)

[Browse Projects](#)

[Nominate Targets](#)

[Watch video tutorials](#)

EDUCATIONAL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESOURCES

With the goal of making MAVEs more accessible, the ETS workstream put together an Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance Literature Library. This resource includes granular reviews and seminal papers relevant to methods at each stage of the MAVE development process (<https://www.varianteffect.org/educational-resources>).

The ETS workstream has also established a nascent **AVE protocols.io workspace** landing page <https://www.protocols.io/workspaces/atlas-of-variant-effects-alliance> which currently includes the following SOPs:

- High Efficiency Yeast Library Transformation
- DIMPLE library generation and assembly protocol
- Converting ssDNA oligos to dsDNA with T4 DNA polymerase
- sgRNA library re-amplification in liquid culture
- Rapid and robust cloning of sgRNA expression plasmids

We encourage all AVE members to share their SOPs. If you would like to contribute a protocol to this collection please see [this guide](#) or contact Benedetta Bolognesi or Andrew Glazer on the AVE slack channel to learn more.

The Alliance also provides **educational videos** which are free to view on our [youtube channel](#). The most viewed workshop video to date is an [Introduction to Deep Mutational Scanning](#) by Kenny Matreyek (2.3K views). Another popular and recent addition to our educational video library is an [Animated Introduction to Deep Mutational Scanning](#) (over 300 views) which was created by high school student Tyler Born (summer volunteer at the Department of Genome Sciences at the University of Washington, Seattle, USA).

COMPUTATIONAL RESOURCES

An important challenge in the rapidly growing variant effects field is keeping up with the huge number of new computational tools that are continuously being published. Two new resources were developed this year by the Analysis, Modelling and Prediction (AMP) workstream, with the goal of increasing accessibility and awareness of computational tools associated with variant effect prediction and MAVE data analysis.

First, a Variant Effect Predictors (VEPs) page (<https://www.varianteffect.org/veps>) was created, which contains some general guidance and background on the use of VEP, and a large table attempting to catalog and classify the many different algorithms that have been released for computationally predicting variant effects. While most tools are focused on predicting the effects of single amino acid substitutions, either in terms of pathogenicity or protein stability, going forward, AMP would like to incorporate more tools focused on non-missense variation in proteins, as well as tools designed to predict the effects of non-coding variants.

AMP also compiled a large set of published benchmarking studies that have assessed the relative performance of tools. Another page (<https://www.varianteffect.org/analysis-tools>) was created to track the various computational tools now available for the analysis of MAVE data, both for scoring variant effects, and other aspects of MAVE data analysis. We appreciate any feedback on other tools or information you think should be included on these pages.

FUNDING ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Brotman Baty Institute (BBI) and the Department of Genome Sciences at the University of Washington, Seattle, USA are the institutional and administrative headquarters for the AVE Alliance.

Along with support from the Brotman Baty Institute, [NHGRI](#) has provided initial seed funding for the Alliance through a Center of Excellence in Genome Science grant (NIH NHGRI RM1HG010461).

“Thus, for clinicians and researchers there exists a path to a world where VUSs are largely eliminated, in line with the NHGRI’s bold prediction. The pace at which we walk this path, and thus whether we are able to achieve the goal of largely eliminating VUSs by 2030, is largely a consequence of the choices made now and in the next few years.”

Excerpt from ‘Will variants of uncertain significance still exist in 2030?’ - Rhem and Fowler

WHAT TO LOOK FOR IN 2024

- Rare Disease Podcast! Spearheaded by ETS workstream member Alex Nguyen Ba
- 7th Annual [Mutational Scanning Symposium](#) at the Broad Institute, May 22-24, 2024
- Variant Effects Seminar Series speakers lined up for 2024 include;
 - ▶ “Understanding and engineering bacteriophages by exploring sequence-function landscapes” - Phil Huss
 - ▶ “Independent benchmarking of variant effect predictors with deep mutational scanning datasets” - Ben Livesey
 - ▶ “Accurate proteome-wide missense variant effect prediction with AlphaMissense” - Joshua Pan
 - ▶ “A brief primer on multiplex assays of variant effect (MAVEs) with application to long QT syndrome variants” Ayesha Muhammad
- Upgrades and enhancements to our central data repository
- New LinkedIn account (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/atlas-of-variant-effects-alliance/>)

OPPORTUNITIES TO ENGAGE AND CONNECT

- Join the Alliance (<https://www.varianteffect.org/membership>)
- Consider supporting us! <https://www.varianteffect.org/donate>
- Participate and/or present at the monthly Variant Effects Seminar Series ([VESS](#))
- Attend and/or present at the [Annual Mutational Scanning Symposium](#)
- Watch educational videos on our [YouTube channel](#)
- Check out our free resources page <https://www.varianteffect.org/resources>
- Register your project or gene of interest on [MaveRegistry](#)
- Deposit your variant effect maps in [MaveDB](#)
- Join a workstream or committee. Workstreams open membership on an ad-hoc basis. Open calls can be found under the membership tab on our [website](#).
- Propose a new working or focus group or initiative! (reach out directly to program manager Lara Muffley muffley@uw.edu to discuss.)
- Follow and interact
 - Twitter/X <https://twitter.com/varianteffects> (@varianteffects)
 - LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/atlas-of-variant-effects-alliance/>
- [Members](#) of the Alliance can join AVE Slack and post in one of the open channels:

- ▶ #educational_resources
- ▶ #general
- ▶ #introductions
- ▶ #job_announcements
- ▶ #literature
- ▶ #random
- ▶ #tips-tricks-troubleshooting
- ▶ #variant-effects-seminar-series

Report prepared by:
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Atlas of Variant Effects Alliance Program Manager

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Thank You!